

«ÚZLIKSIZ BILIMLENDIRIW SISTEMASINDA ARALÍQTAN OQÍTÍWDÍN INTEGRACIYASÍ»

atamasındaqı IV Xalıqaralıq ilimiy-teoriyalıq konferenciya

FOLK ART IS A COMPREHENSIVE TOOL FOR DEVELOPING CHILDREN

Galiya Taubayeva,
Scientific supervisor,
galiya_63@bk.ru
Republic of Kazakhstan, Almaty

Sagyn Ulbosyn Kenesbaykyzy,
Ulbolsyn.sagyn@mail.ru

Abai Kaznpu,
Specialty preschool education
and upbringing
2 course Master's degree

Annotation: The article explores the importance of oral Kazakh folk literature in the development, cognitive growth, and education of preschool children. The ability of children to express their thoughts through artistic means such as fairy tales, riddles, proverbs, and sayings is assessed, along with their understanding and comparison of these works. Since folk traditions are the sole cultural heritage of the country in terms of history, culture, art, and economics, it is crucial to enhance the scientific and pedagogical justification for preschoolers in accordance with the demands of modern society.

Keywords: lullaby, riddles, proverbs, fairy tales, sayings.

Introduction. In the context of worldwide globalization, preserving individual identity and enhancing national characteristics in line with modern civilization requirements are highly important. To ensure that the spiritual values of the people withstand the influx of information and do not fall behind foreign influences, it is essential to strengthen the knowledge of the younger generation. Priority issues include promoting traditions, customs, role models, educating the nation, understanding the country's history, culture, and reviving art.

With the changes in societal development, public education is becoming part of the global educational sphere and undergoing modernization [1]. Various measures have been implemented to reorganize education based on societal interests, update the educational and upbringing content, develop literature and culture [2], create new preschool curricula, teaching materials, and integrate them into educational institutions [3, 4]. The main aim is to cultivate well-rounded individuals who are enthusiastic about serving society. These objectives are outlined in state documents such as the Constitution of the Republic of Kazakhstan, the Language Law, the Education Law, and others [5, 6, 7].

«ÚZLIKSIZ BILIMLENDIRIW SISTEMASINDA ARALIQTAN OQITWDIŃ INTEGRACIYASI»

atamasındaǵı IV Xalıqaralıq ilimiy-teoriyalıq konferenciya

According to the Encyclopedia of Kazakh literature, Kazakh children's folklore serves as a crucial instrument in the oral education of children, providing them with moral guidance and psychological development. This folklore encompasses various genres such as lullabies, riddles, poems, proverbs, fairy tales, legends, and heroic songs [8].

Teaching Kazakh folk oral literature to preschool children requires special attention and consideration of each genre. These examples of folklore play a significant role in expanding children's knowledge, stimulating their imagination, and developing their appreciation for beauty and virtue. It is important to carefully select and curate works of oral literature that are appropriate for reading, considering factors such as volume, content, genre, language characteristics, as well as the age and psychological traits of the child.

According to M. Zhumabayev: "In the Kazakh language, the history of the Kazakh Sary sairan steppe is as clear as a windless night, as sharp as a whirlwind, the way of life in the yellow steppe, the unhurried, unsociable calm character – everything is visible", the history and way of life of the Kazakh Sary sairan steppe are prominently portrayed in the Kazakh language and the works of Kazakh word art [9]. A. Baitursynov highlighted the importance of knowledge in primary education and the significance of language in an individual's life: "A person needs the same knowledge that is learned in primary school as he needs the language, ears and hands" [10].

M. Gabdullin emphasized the oral literature of the Kazakh people as a valuable cultural heritage that originated in ancient times and often centered around children [11]. Sh. Akhmetov is one of the only research scientists who has scientifically studied the impact of Kazakh oral literature on children, role models and teaching. He revealed the meaning of Kazakh folklore, focused on each genre separately, gave a definition for each, described its own characteristics, substantiated the function of the child in the development of intelligence, imagination, cognition, language.

In his work, "Qazaq balalar adebieti tarihinin ocherkisi" Sh. Akhmetov emphasizes the crucial role of oral literature as the foundation of children's literature. He highlights the significance of folklore, considering it as the invaluable treasure and origin of children's literature. Sh. Akhmetov categorizes children's folklore into different stages. The first stage begins with lullabies, followed by the second stage of presentation songs. The third stage aims to familiarize children with their immediate environment, including insect life and animal husbandry. The fourth stage focuses on

«ÚZLIKSIZ BILIMLENDIRIW SISTEMASINDA ARALÍQTAN OQÍTÍWDÍŃ INTEGRACIYASÍ»

atamasındaǵı IV Xalıqaralıq ilimiy-teoriyalıq konferenciya

introducing children to the seasons and their surroundings. The fifth stage utilizes playful methods to teach children to speak correctly and clearly. The sixth stage is devoted to developing children's intellect, incorporating mystery genres.

Sh. Akhmetov asserts that the formation of children's worldview, comprehension of lifestyle, education, mental development, and language proficiency can be divided into stages based on the saying, "mother's milk grows, mother's language grows thoughts." He highlights the significance of folk poems, misleading poems, lying poems, proverbs, riddles, and fairy tales in shaping children's understanding. Furthermore, in his work on Kazakh children's literature, Sh. Akhmetov examines the aesthetic ideals present in oral literature, specifically focusing on the aesthetics of lullabies and presentation songs. He also explores the wisdom, educational value, proverbs, riddles, and moral meaning conveyed through folk tales, particularly those featuring four animals [12].

The development of preschool children's speech is considered a fundamental requirement, and Kazakh folklore plays a crucial role in this aspect. The surrounding environment, through folk works, helps children understand intricacies and develop cognitive abilities such as imagination, thinking, memory, and language. Oral literature provides ample opportunities for child-rearing by teaching them that moral qualities lead to achieving dreams, while bad behavior and alien acts bring harm and expose one to evil.

The results of the study. The first form of communication that a baby experiences is the mother's lullaby, which conveys the musical melody of their native language. The lullaby serves as an initial step towards comforting the baby and instilling in them the qualities of kindness, sensitivity, and tenderness. Through the lullaby, a mother creates a nurturing environment for her child, conveying their dreams and aspirations for the future, comparing their child to the noblest beings in the world, and singing them a song.

Children also engage with playful poems, such as "Kuyr-kuyr, kuyrmash," "Ushti-Ushti" and "Who needs it?," which further expand their knowledge, foster observation skills, enhance intelligence, and improve diction.

The poem "Kuyr-kuyr, kuyrmash" introduces children to the names of their fingers, including the thumb, index finger, middle finger, ring finger, and little finger. It also uses similes to describe each finger, comparing them to various objects such as a baby duck or a rattling noise. This poem emphasizes that our fingers have different characteristics and purposes that we may not always notice. For example, the thumb

«ÚZLIKSIZ BILIMLENDIRIW SISTEMASINDA ARALIQTAN OQITWDIŃ INTEGRACIYASI»

atamasındaǵı IV Xalıqaralıq ilimiy-teoriyalıq konferenciya

is associated with excellence or perfection, while the index finger is seen as a guiding or disciplining force. Through this poem, children are encouraged to name and compare other objects in their surroundings, stimulating their imagination and enhancing their thinking skills.

Similarly, poems about animals, birds, and natural phenomena like “One Pot of Milk” (“Bir qazan sut”), “Raven, Raven, Raven” (“Qarga, qarga, qargalar”), “Frog” (“Baqa”), and “Camel, Camel, Camel” (“Tuye, tuye, tuyeler”) broaden children’s knowledge and evoke feelings of compassion and care. For instance, in the poem “One Pot of Milk” (“Bir qazan sut”) children learn about the posture and sounds of birds during their activities, as well as words that represent those sounds. This encourages children to pay attention to the sounds made by other birds and animals and fosters their curiosity about the natural world.

Game poems are intended to educate children in various skills such as creativity, imagination, dexterity, and problem-solving. These poems engage children in different actions and movements, fostering excitement and joy as they participate.

Another important category of children’s poems are counting poems like “Count” (“Samaq”), which help children expand their vocabulary, understand rhyme, and learn the names and order of numbers. These poems also involve finger movements, allowing children to practice counting and follow along with the poem.

Folklore also includes children’s tongue twisters, which consist of challenging sounds and words that can be difficult to pronounce. These tongue twisters help children improve their pronunciation skills, distinguish words by their meanings, and speak quickly and fluently without straining. They also encourage clear and careful speech, ensuring that the meaning of words is not distorted. Tongue twisters are an interesting genre that introduces children to various scenes and phenomena in their surroundings.

One example of a genre that enhances both thinking abilities and language skills is riddles. Riddles have been a part of Kazakh folklore for a long time and are characterized by their figurative and thought-provoking nature. They encourage children to think creatively and expand their knowledge as they try to solve the riddle.

In Baitursynov’s work “Adebiet tanıtqış” he discusses the significance of riddles as a means of communication in Kazakh culture [13]. Riddles have been used since ancient times and serve various purposes. They were utilized as a game to test and develop oratorical skills among adults, as well as to teach children about the

«ÚZLIKSIZ BILIMLENDIRIW SISTEMASINDA ARALIQTAN OQITWDIŃ INTEGRACIYASI»

atamasındaǵı IV Xalıqaralıq ilimiy-teoriyalıq konferenciya

mysteries of the world and enhance their knowledge, imagination, language abilities, and quick thinking. Riddles capture attention and offer a unique way of conveying information.

Proverbs and sayings are the result of wisdom accumulated over years, forming part of our literary heritage passed down from one generation to the next. They are a valuable treasure of wise thoughts and ancestral words. Despite their small size, they encompass a vast amount of knowledge, profound insights, impactful language, and rich traditions. Within these 90 words lies the accumulated experience and wisdom of generations, serving as a guiding light that instructs and enlightens us in life. Proverbs forewarn and steer us towards what is right and wrong, criticising or praising accordingly. Parents utilise these proverbs as a means of educating their children from a young age, instilling moral values and shaping their perspective on life and relationships. Proverbs and sayings provide a model for children to emulate, teaching them how to express complex ideas in a concise form and emphasizing the power of words.

Fairy tales play a significant role in a child's cognitive, linguistic, and imaginative development. When children hear or read fairy tales, they reflect on the underlying meaning and try to interpret it in their own way. They explore the structure and language of the fairy tale, imagining different events and the characters' behaviors and actions. In order to comprehend and illustrate the story, children give the text deep meaning, mentally analyze it, remember specific scenes and events, and form their own opinions about the characters' actions and relationships. Fairy tales allow children to develop their imagination and language skills, especially in situations where there is a lack of children's literature. They also preserve and revive forgotten words and expressions from the people. The value of a fairy tale depends on the specific needs it fulfills, whether it is enhancing language skills or encouraging children to think and express themselves creatively. According to A. Baitursynov, a literary researcher, Kazakh fairy tales serve the purpose of making stories logical and interesting through human imagination. These tales explore concepts such as good and evil, friendship and enmity, honesty and dishonesty, heroism and cowardice, dexterity and shorthand, allowing us to compare and learn from their respective qualities [13].

The renowned writer M. Auezov states that fairy tales reflect the country's worldview over time, conveying moral lessons and idealizing good while condemning evil. He states: “.. a fairy tale refers to a wholesale fairy tale that

«ÚZLIKSIZ BILIMLENDIRIW SISTEMASINDA ARALIQTAN OQITIVDIN INTEGRACIYASI»

atamasındaǵı IV Xalıqaralıq ilimiy-teoriyalıq konferenciya

expresses the attitude of a country to the world in a long time, shows a well-known trace of this attitude, then expresses the way of a particular country, tells a special example, buries evil, raises good" [14]. A. Konyratbayev, a respected scientist, emphasizes that Kazakh folklore provides profound insights and guidance, addressing human education and societal issues. These tales promote love for the people, appreciation for labor and courage, kindness towards friends, resilience against enemies, and a sense of national unity. Ultimately, they aim to shape individuals, especially the younger generation, by instilling qualities necessary for personal growth and fostering an appreciation for art and the country [15].

Conclusions In essence, folklore has a positive impact on children by allowing them to immerse themselves freely in the world, understand their native culture, appreciate the beauty of their homeland, comprehend the collective wisdom of their people, and learn moral, artistic, and aesthetic lessons. By popularizing and embracing the spiritual wealth and noble heritage of the people, children have the opportunity to develop as individuals [16]. Folk pedagogy principles, accumulated and practiced throughout centuries, have contributed to raising children and embodying the ideals of collective wisdom, moral understanding, and aesthetic sensibility. Ultimately, the goal is to mold the image of a well-rounded and virtuous individual in the minds and dreams of future generations. This ideal holds value in its harmonious integration into universal knowledge and understanding. Examples of oral literature are an essential tool for fostering comprehensive education, nurturing children's thoughts, intelligence, and worldview.

Used literature:

1. The Address of President of the Republic of Kazakhstan K. Tokayev to the people of Kazakhstan "A Just state. United Nation. Blessed society" – Astana, 2022
2. "On approval of the model for the development of preschool education and training" (Order of the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan dated March 15 No. 137).
3. "State mandatory standard of preschool education and training". Order of the Ministry of Education of the Republic of Kazakhstan dated August 03, 2021 No. 348). – Astana, 2022 .
4. "On approval of standard curricula of preschool education and Training" / Order of the minister of Education of the Republic of Kazakhstan dated October 14, 2022 No. 422. – Astana, 2022

«ÚZLIKSIZ BILIMLENDIRIW SISTEMASINDA ARALIQTAN OQITIVDIN INTEGRACIYASI»

atamasındaǵı IV Xalıqaralıq ilimiy-teoriyalıq konferenciya

5. Constitution Of The Republic Of Kazakhstan. (30.08.1995 with changes from 08.08.2022). – Astana, 2022.
6. The Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan on Languages (law of the Republic of Kazakhstan dated 11.07.1997 No. 151-I 2008.21.11.)
7. The Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan on Education. 27.07.2007 No. 319-III (as amended on 31.07.2018). – Astana, 2018 .
8. Kazakh literature (Qazaq adabietini). Encyclopedia. Almaty: Kazakhstan Development Institute, 1999. – 750 p.
9. Zhumabayev M. Pedagogy (Pedagogika). – Almaty: Ana tili: 1992. – 160 p. Gabdullin M. Oral literature of the Kazakh people (Qazaq halqynyn auyz adabietini). – Almaty: Sanat, 1996 – P. 78-102.
10. Baitursynov A. Language lessons (Til tagylymy). – Almaty: Ana tili, 1992. – 448 p.
11. Gabdullin M. Qazaq halkynyn auyz adabietini. – Almaty: Sanat, 1996 – P.78-102.
12. Akhmetov Sh. Anthology of children's literature (Balalar adabietinin hristomatiyasi). – Almaty: Mektep, 1980.
13. Baitursynov A. Adabiet tanıtqish, – Almaty: Atamura, 2003. – 208 p.
14. Auezov M. Ertegiler. – Almaty: Ana tili 1998.- 148 p.
15. Konyratbayev A. History of Kazakh folklore (Qazaq folklorynyn taryhy) (compiled and prefaced by T. Konyratbayev). – Almaty: Ana tili, 1991. – 288 p.
16. Taubayeva G. Qazaq balalar adabietini. Manual. – Almaty: Ulagat. 2022.- 160 p.

